

The Cherenkov Telescopes Array: fundamental physics and instrumentation.

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Abstract

We review the potentiality of the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) in measuring dark matter, in imposing limits on Lorentz Invariance Violation, in characterizing the extragalactic background light, in studying the Large Magellanic Cloud and the Galactic center. It is also shown the development of instrumentation for CTA in Brazil. The paper focuses on the CTA's targets to which the authors have an important contribution.

1 Introduction

Gamma-rays constitute the highest energy form of electromagnetic radiation, at least a billion times more energetic than visible light. Long before the development of the first instruments and satellites able to detect gamma emission from cosmic sources in the 1960's, scientists had already predicted that the universe should produce copious quantities of gamma-rays by different processes, most of them related to the acceleration of charged particles known as cosmic rays.¹

Gamma-rays and cosmic rays are known to be produced in the interstellar and intergalactic gas, supernova explosions, pulsars, stellar-mass black holes (in our Galaxy), super-massive black holes at the cores of active galaxies and gamma-ray bursts (GRBs). Apart from these sources, dark matter annihilation in certain channels is expected to produce gamma-rays which could be detected by space based instruments and ground telescopes.

Particles with energy above 10^9 are the messengers of the non-thermal Universe. In addition to the radiation emitted by stars and produced predominantly by thermal or collisional emission, we know that some forms of radiation are independent of gas temperature and require the action of a collective process of concentration of energy on a small population of particles. The main evidence for these processes is undoubtedly the energy spectrum of gamma and cosmic rays which cannot be reduced to a thermal process. Gamma-rays and cosmic rays are an important piece of information in our task to describe the Universe and its fundamental laws since the energy density of cosmic particles² is of the same order of magnitude as the energy density of stars light and the galactic magnetic fields [1].

Gamma-ray detection by Cherenkov telescopes is a well established technique that has contributed significantly to our understanding of several phenomena in astroparticle physics in the last two decades. The history of ground-based gamma-ray observatories can be divided in three phases: pioneer, stereo and large sets of telescopes. Currently, we are in the last phase, in which an international consortium proposed the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA) array.

The pioneering experiment Whipple [2] began operations in 1982 and demonstrated the efficiency of the technique. The stereoscopic phase started around the year 2000. The current experiments H.E.S.S. [3], CANGAROO [4], VERITAS [5] and MAGIC [6] have demonstrated how the joint operation of the telescopes may increase the sensitivity, improve the selection efficiency of gamma-rays against noise of charged cosmic rays and reduce the angular error in the positioning of the source. These advances enabled the study of various mechanisms which are inaccessible through other techniques and the detection of new sources with emission in the TeV region. The operation of such experiments in the last decade has caused a revolution in the understanding of several mechanisms, which can be verified by an important raise in the number of publications in this area.

¹The word cosmic rays is used in this project to define charged cosmic particles

²cosmic particles = gamma-rays + cosmic rays

Figure 1: CTA artistic view.

The success of the stereoscopic phase has led to the proposal of CTA [7]. CTA will be an array of telescopes of three different sizes with ten times more sensitivity than any current gamma-ray instrument, with much wider energy coverage (between 20 GeV and 300 TeV), unprecedented angular and energy resolution, and much wider field of view. It is proposed as an observatory in two sites, one in the Southern (Paranal, Chile) and one in the Northern hemisphere (Canarian Island, Spain). Figure 1 shows the artistic view of CTA telescopes.

The scientific scope of CTA covers several crucial questions in astrophysics and high energy particle physics. Among them, the origin of cosmic rays, the physics of compact objects, like pulsars and black holes, binary stars, supernovae, giant molecular clouds, dark matter, Lorentz Invariance and GRBs. In this context, the CTA was considered a priority in all evaluation panels to which it was submitted, including: ASPERA (ASTroParticle ERAnet), Astronete (a comprehensive long-term planning for the development of European astronomy) and ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) in Europe, and PASAG (Particle Astrophysics Scientific Assessment Group) and ASTRO2010 (Decadal survey information of the American Astronomical Society) in the United States. It is worthwhile to mention here the opinion of Astronete on the CTA: “The Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA), an array of optical telescopes to detect gamma-rays from high energy black holes and other extreme phenomena in the Universe. Building on existing successful European experiments, the CTA - the first true observatory at such energies - is expected to bring a breakthrough in our understanding of the origin and production of high energy gamma-rays.”

Currently CTA is in the transition phase from prototypes to mass construction. Several prototypes have been tested and the final configuration is being set. In the next three years, CTA will be built simultaneously in both sites. In five years, CTA is going to start to produce high quality science. Brazil joined CTA in 2010 with a small group of scientists. Today we are more than fifty member scientists with strong participation in construction and science opti-

mization. This paper describes the interest of the authors in CTA science and the efforts we have been doing in the last years.

2 The Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA)

CTA’s detection of gamma-rays is based on the image of the air shower produced by the particles cascading down in the atmosphere. Three types of telescopes are required to cover the energy range from 20 GeV to 300 TeV. For its core energy range (100 GeV to 10 TeV), CTA is proposing 40 Medium-Sized Telescopes (MSTs). Eight Large-Sized Telescopes (LSTs) and 70 Small-Sized Telescopes (SSTs) are planned to extend the energy range below 100 GeV and above 10 TeV, respectively. The MSTs and LSTs will be installed on both sites, while the SSTs will only be installed on the southern hemisphere site. Figure 2 illustrates the proposed layout for both sites.

The Cherenkov light produced in the shower is reflected by the mirrors and detected by cameras. Each telescope has its own variation of camera, but the designs are all driven by the brightness and short duration of the Cherenkov light flash. A Cherenkov light flash lasts only a few nanoseconds and is extremely faint. The cameras are sensitive to these faint flashes and use extremely fast exposures to capture the light. Photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) or silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs) equip the focal plane of the telescopes.

CTA will provide a very wide energy range and excellent angular resolution and sensitivity in comparison to any existing gamma-ray detector (see figure 3). Energies up to 300 TeV will push CTA beyond the edge of the known electromagnetic spectrum, providing a completely new view of the sky.

The CTA observatory will be open to proposals from the scientific community. However, during its first decade of operation, approximately 40% of the available observing time will be dedicated to a Core Programme. This programme consists of several Key Science Projects (KSPs) - major multi-purpose

Figure 2: CTA telescope layout.

Figure 3: Left: CTA angular resolution. Right: CTA differential sensitivity.

observations designed to efficiently address a broad range of science questions [8]. The authors of this paper are leading the preparations for three out of fifteen papers under preparation concerning the nine proposed Key Science Projects.

3 The Large Magellanic Cloud

The Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) is a satellite galaxy of the Milky Way with unique characteristics that make it a valuable target for γ ray experiments. Located in the southern hemisphere at a Galactic latitude of -32.9° , off the galactic plane, and with a disk shape almost faced on (with a small inclination angle of $30\text{-}40^\circ$) it is one of the nearest, very active star forming galaxies, at a distance of about 50kpc.

Although the star forming rate of the LMC is one tenth of the Milky Way, it is distributed in only two percent of its volume. Several star forming regions are known within the LMC, such as 30 Doradus, among plenty of HII regions, bubbles and shells that have been observed in many wavelengths. It is known that the LMC contains more than 60 Supernova Remnants(SNRs) and Pulsar Wind Nebulae(PWNe) making it a perfect target for population studies and probing the transport of cosmic rays.

Because of its proximity, it is observed as an extended object, making it possible to distinguish individual gamma-ray sources from diffuse emission. For the reasons above, the LMC has been identified as a Key Science Project for CTA.

A full astrophysical model in order to forecast detection of the LMC with the Southern Array of CTA has been developed which includes point sources, intrinsically diffuse background (due to Cosmic Ray propagation within the LMC), and a diffuse caused by undetected point sources has been developed and most recently a population of Pulsar Wind Nebulae (PWNe). The analysis has converged into a single Consortium paper which is currently (2019) in its writing phases.

4 The Galactic Center

Among all the high-energy environments of our Galaxy, the Galactic Center (GC) region is definitely the richest. It harbours a large amount of high-energy emitters, including the closest supermassive black hole, a cosmic Pevatron, dense molecular clouds, strong star-forming activity, multiple supernova remnants and pulsar wind nebulae, arc-like radio structures, as well as the base of what may be large-scale galactic outflows. It stands out as one of the most studied regions of the sky in nearly every wavelength, and has some of the deepest exposures with high-energy observatories (H.E.S.S., Fermi-LAT, Chandra, XMM, INTEGRAL), which have provided an enormous amount of scientific results. Moreover, this region is also expected to be the brightest source of dark matter (DM) annihilations in the gamma-ray sky by several orders of magnitude. Even considering the contamination from standard astrophysical sources, it is one of the most promising targets to detect the presence of new massive particles.

For all these reasons, the Galactic Center region has been selected as a CTA Key Science Project. The project is comprised of a deep survey of the GC region containing two small survey regions: a deep exposure close in to the central source, centered on Sgr A*, and an extended region starting at the edge of the deep exposure and extending to the edge of the Galactic bulge (see Fig. 4). This survey of the GC region is considered key science for both scientific and technical reasons. The proposed observations will require a large time commitment spread over several years providing the deepest exposure of the GC region ever produced in the VHE domain. The broad variety of targets and topics is expected to give rise to high-impact scientific results for years

Figure 4: *Left*: A schematic representation of the Galactic Center KSP. This figure shows one possible observation strategy for CTA. The deep survey region is shown in red, with the Galactic bulge extension shown in cyan (with each circle representing a 6° field of view for a typical CTA configuration) (from Ref. [8]). *Right*: A simulated view of the inner 4° of the Galactic Center region as seen by CTA (excess events above 100 GeV after cosmic-ray background subtraction, with PSF smoothing).

to come. As part of this KSP, the CTA Consortium will organize coordinated observations in other wavebands that will permit detailed variability studies and constitute an invaluable legacy data set.

A Consortium paper discussing how CTA will explore the entire high-energy astrophysical content of the GC region is currently under preparation. Tests of CTA capabilities to study the high-energy emissions at the GC, and how it can discriminate between different production mechanisms are being developed based on realistic simulations, data analysis and interpretation [9].

5 Dark Matter

Within the framework of the Λ Cold Dark Matter scenario, most of the matter in the Universe is made by an unknown substance, particles whose nature very likely lies beyond the Standard Model of Particle Physics. Within the many possible explanations put forward, and currently being tested experimentally, one that has received much attention within the community over the last decades is that the Dark Matter may be made of Weakly Interacting Massive Particles (often referred to as WIMPs).

Besides their theoretical motivations, WIMPs (as well as other types of candidates) offer the phenomenological advantage of being self-annihilating into standard model particles, producing a shower of primaries and secondaries that would interact with the environment at the place of annihilation.

This is particularly interesting to high energy astrophysicist for the two reasons: *a*) the mass scale of WIMPs (and therefore the energy of the annihilation products) lies above the GeV, and potentially up to tens of TeV, and *b*) the fact that the annihilation would be more sizable in environments richest of DM, namely within astrophysical structures such as galaxies and clusters, where the telescopes would point anyways.

The products of DM annihilation would therefore show up as an additional, “exotic” component on the top of the astrophysical one, and depend on the nature of the Dark Matter through its annihilation cross-section, its mass, its couplings to the standard model, all eventually affecting the spectrum of gamma-rays emitted. Searches of Dark Matter annihilation (or decay) have therefore become one important tool for particle physicists trying to identify a yet unknown fundamental component, a tool which relies heavily on the characterization of astrophysical targets, and knowledge associate to all steps of high-energy astrophysical detection.

More specifically, this “indirect” search for dark matter signals with CTA has several possible astrophysical targets, each with its own inherent advantages and disadvantages. The observational strategy proposed for the CTA Dark Matter Programme is focused first on collecting a significant amount of data on the Galactic Center, followed by complementary observations of one or more dSph galaxies, the LMC and galaxy clusters. The GC, the LMC, and galaxy clusters are valuable targets both for dark matter searches and for studies of non-thermal processes in astrophysical sources. Data will be searched for

continuum emission and line features, and strategies will be adopted according to the findings. Discoveries will modify any strategies defined a priori. Below we describe some of the most compelling targets for CTA searches with a strong Brazilian participation, namely the Galactic Center, dwarf spheroidal galaxies and the LMC.

5.1 The Galactic Center

The Galactic Center is one of the most interesting regions to look for a DM annihilation signal. Due to its proximity and very high dark matter content, this region is expected to be the brightest source of DM annihilations in the γ -ray sky. Even considering the contamination from standard astrophysical sources, it is one of the most promising targets to detect the presence of WIMPs. However, the search for a DM-induced signal toward the GC region has been inconclusive so far, partly impeded by the detection of multiple emissions due to particle accelerators, including several major discoveries [10–13]. Hence, the detailed studies, measurements and precise modeling of the high-energy emissions from this region under the GC KSP main project are of the utmost importance, and will greatly contribute to enhance the sensitivity of DM searches towards the center of the Milky Way.

The current observation CTA strategy of the GC consists of multiple grid pointings with offsets from the GC position of about $\pm 1.3^\circ$ to cover the central 5° as uniformly as possible. The total observation time of the central deep survey will be of around 500 hours and it is well suited to probe cuspy profile dark matter distributions. Then further 300 hours are proposed for astrophysics covering up to latitudes $\pm 10^\circ$. These data will also be included in the analysis for dark matter to improve the sensitivity for cored dark matter density profiles.

The sensitivity predictions for observations in the Galactic Halo are shown in Figure 5. The left-hand plot shows the sensitivity for different annihilation modes (W^+W^- , $b\bar{b}$, $\tau^+\tau^-$, $t\bar{t}$), assuming an Einasto profile for the GC halo DM density distribution. It can be seen that CTA will be able to probe a thermal-relic cross-section ($\langle\sigma v\rangle \sim 3 \times 10^{-26} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) for all models with DM masses $\gtrsim 200 \text{ GeV}$ in most annihilation channels. The right-hand plot of Fig. 5 shows CTA sensitivity in the monochromatic line search assuming two different dark matter distribution profiles (Einasto and isothermal). Here again CTA will provide unprecedented sensitivity, and as no known standard astrophysical sources would produce such sharp energetic features, the discrimination against background is easier in line searches compared to the continuum emission search.

5.2 Dwarf spheroidal galaxies

Dwarf Spheroidal galaxies have been long considered a prime target for DM searches: with their extremely high Mass-to-Luminosity ratio, and the null presence of known astrophysical sources of high energy gamma-rays within them, they offer a unique chance to identify photons potentially arising from DM annihilation or decay.

Figure 5: *Left*: CTA sensitivity for $\langle\sigma v\rangle$ from observation of the Galactic halo for different annihilation modes as indicated. The dashed horizontal lines approximate the level of the thermal cross-section. *Right*: Sensitivity of CTA to monochromatic gamma-ray signals from dark matter annihilation, with energy equal to the DM particle mass. For comparison, the currently best limits from Fermi (black triangles) and H.E.S.S. (red dots) are also shown, along with the much discussed line-like feature at around 130 GeV (magenta star). The dashed lines also show the mean upper-limits obtained in case of a Burkert profile. The natural scale for monochromatic gamma-ray signal is highlighted as a black shaded area. Extracted from ref. [8].

Dwarf Spheroidal galaxies have a small angular size, and therefore need specific pointing from Cherenkov Telescopes (unlike survey mode telescopes, such as FERMI, that can continuously collect light from them in any case), and their case has been made into the only Key Science Project specifically dedicated to Dark Matter within the CTA.

The strength of the annihilation (or decay) signal that one expects depends on (besides the physics of the very nature of the Dark Matter that one is addressing) the amount of Dark Matter within the object itself, which is often referred to through a convenient quantity embedding also information on the distance of the galaxy from us, and often referred to as the *J-factor*.

The estimate of the *J-factor* from individual objects is then one of the key-elements of the searches for Dark Matter, and it has been therefore devoted thorough attention in these preliminary stages.

5.3 LMC

The Large Magellanic Cloud, a KSP described in a previous dedicated section, can also be used as a target for the annihilation of Dark Matter. It does not offer the advantages of Dwarf Spheroidal Galaxies: in fact, hosting its own gas cloud and point sources (the latter within the Galaxy itself, or projected into the field of the galaxy itself) there is sizable contamination to the potential DM signal. However, being thoroughly characterized for the sake of the KSP

Figure 6: *Left*: CTA sensitivity to semi-annihilating dark matter with $\chi\chi \rightarrow \chi\phi$, where ϕ decays into bb [14]. *Right*: CTA sensitivity to the Inert Higgs Doublet Model [15].

purposes, additional dedicated studies for the characterization of the DM signal come at low cost, and the potential of one additional target is highly regarded in the DM community for the validation (and falsification) of signals potentially detected elsewhere.

5.4 Semi-Annihilating Dark Matter

Dark matter particles should be stable at cosmological scales and have a lifetime much larger than the age of the universe. In model building endeavours the dark matter stability is typically guaranteed by a discrete Z_2 symmetry. If that is the case dark matter annihilations drive the flux in gamma-rays. Albeit, if larger symmetries are evoked to stabilize the dark matter particle, χ , semi-annihilations are present and might yield sizeable gamma-ray fluxes. One could conceive scenarios where $\chi\chi \rightarrow \chi + \phi$, with ϕ being a scalar field, not necessarily the Higgs boson. Therefore, one would need to assess the Cherenkov Telescope Array sensitivity to semi-annihilating dark matter. In the left-panel of Fig.6 we show a very conservative estimate of the CTA sensitivity to such setup, with ϕ decaying to b-quark pairs, based on [14]. One can clearly see that CTA will constitute the best probe for dark matter masses above few hundred GeV.

5.5 Inert Higgs Doublet Model

The Inert Doublet Model is a model that extends the Standard Model with a second Higgs Doublet odd under a Z_2 symmetry. Such symmetry avoids tree-level flavor changing neutral interactions and automatically makes the lightest neutral scalar of the inert doublet stable and a natural dark matter candidate. The annihilation cross-section is quite large because of the presence of gauge boson interactions, and coannihilation processes involving the charged Higgs and the pseudo-scalar, embedded in the inert doublet, are present and drive

the relic density. Today, the coannihilation processes are absent. Thus one can probe such large annihilation processes with gamma-ray telescopes. Adopting a very modest estimate of the CTA sensitivity, and considering only the points which the relic density and direct detection bounds are satisfied, we show in the right-panel of Fig.6 that CTA will be able to rule out the model up to masses of 3 TeV [15]. Recent sensitivity studies show that CTA will actually provide bounds which are about an order of magnitude better than the ones used in [15]. Hence, if no signal is observed, we can conclusively say that CTA will fiercely exclude the Inert Doublet Model at the TeV scale.

6 Lorentz Invariance Violation

High-sensitivity γ -ray observations at the highest energies can also be used as a test for fundamental physics, such as the Lorentz invariance (LI). Like any other fundamental principle, exploring its limits of validity has been an essential motivation for theoretical and experimental research [16, 17]. The formulation of the quantum theory of gravity is one of the main challenges of physics, and some approaches predict a violation of Lorentz invariance (LIV) at high energy scales [18].

Although LIV signatures are expected to be small, some effects of LIV are expected to increase with energy and distance due to cumulative processes; therefore, astroparticle scenarios provide an unprecedented opportunity for this task due to their very high energies and long distances. Moreover, the CTA unprecedented precision in energy and directional reconstruction will generate an extraordinary opportunity for LIV tests [19, 20].

The spontaneous symmetry breaking of the Lorentz symmetry in the standard model of particles [16, 21, 22] or the introduction of an explicit Lorentz violating term in the SM Lagrangian [23] can induce modifications to the particle dispersion relation (MDR). A phenomenological generalization of these LIV effects converges on the introduction of a general function of the energy and momentum [24]. Although, there are several forms of MDR for different particles and underlying LIV-theories, some of them may lead to similar phenomenology, which have been proven to be useful for LIV tests in extreme environments such as astroparticle scenarios [25]. In this line of thought, a family of MDRs can be addressed. So that, for photons, the MDR is

$$E_\gamma^2 - p_\gamma^2 = \pm |\delta_{\gamma,n}| E_\gamma^{n+2}, \quad (1)$$

where E_γ is the photon energy, p_γ its momentum, and $p_\gamma \approx E_\gamma$ at first leading order in $\delta_{\gamma,n}$, to the high energy of the astroparticles involved. $\delta_{\gamma,n}$ is the LIV photon parameter, where n , is the leading order of the correction from the underlying theory. In some effective field theories, $\delta_{\gamma,n} = \zeta_\gamma^{(n)}/M$, where $\zeta_a^{(n)}$ are the LIV coefficients, and M is the energy scale of the new physics, such as, the Planck energy scale, $E_{\text{Pl}} \approx 1.22 \times 10^{28} \text{eV}$, or some Quantum Gravity energy scale, E_{QG} . The sign \pm stands for the so-called *superluminal* (+) or *subluminal*

(-) dominant phenomena. For simplicity, when $n > 0$, it is common to write the LIV parameter in some LIV energy scale, $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(n)} = (\delta_{\gamma,n})^{1/n}$.

The derived physics from the correction in Eq. (1) can lead to shifts at the minimum background photon energy that allows the pair production process, given by

$$\epsilon^{th} = \frac{m_e^2}{4E_\gamma K(1-K)} - \frac{1}{4}\delta_{\gamma,n} E_\gamma^{n+1}, \quad (2)$$

where K is the inelasticity of the process.

Equation (2) considers LIV only in photons. However, if LIV is also included for electrons and positrons, $\delta_{\gamma,n} \rightarrow \delta_n^{\text{tot}}$, where δ_n^{tot} is a linear combination of the LIV coefficients of the electrons, positrons, and photons, so that, the LIV phenomenology derived in both cases is preserved, for a further discussion, see [26] and references therein. Eq. (2) also considers only subluminal LIV photons ($\delta_{\gamma,n} < 0$), which forecast a recovery in the spectrum of TeV-sources that can be measured by the current γ -ray telescopes [17, 27–29]. Although, no LIV signal of this type has been found, strong exclusion limits have been reported. Taking $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(n)} = (\delta_{\gamma,n})^{1/n}$, the best 2 sigma limits on E_{LIV} by testing these subluminal LIV effects were found to be $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(1)} \geq 12 \times 10^{28}$ eV and $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(2)} \geq 2.4 \times 10^{21}$ eV [29].

As an example of the CTA potential to test LIV [20], in Fig. 7 there are GAMMAPY simulations for CTA North observations of 1ES 0229+200 as black points, assuming the intrinsic source spectrum as a power law with exponential cut-off,

$$dN/dE = N_0(E/E_0)^{-\Gamma} \exp(-E/E_{\text{cut}}), \quad (3)$$

where $N_0 = 1.45 \times 10^{-12}$ TeV $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$, $E_0 = 1.6$ TeV, $\Gamma = 1.45$ and $E_{\text{cut}} = 40$ TeV. The EBL model from Ref. [30] is assumed. In Fig. 7(a), results without the LIV effect are shown, while Fig. 7(b) includes the LIV effect for the scenario where $n = 2$ and $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(2)} = 5 \times 10^{20}$ eV, through Eq. (2). There are similar effects for $E_{\text{LIV}}^{(1)} \sim E_{\text{Pl}}$. For comparison, the current IACT (HESS, MAGIC, and VERITAS) and CTA sensitivity thresholds are shown in the dashed-dotted lines. It is clear from Fig. 7, that CTA will improve the possibility to detect a LIV signal from the previous IACT. In the particular scenario with the LIV effect in Fig. 7(b), the recovery in the spectrum at TeV energies would be clearly detected by CTA. Preliminary results from the simulations of CTA observations of the nearby blazar Mrk 501 can be found in Ref. [19].

Both preliminary results from the simulations of CTA observations of the Mrk501 and 1ES 200+209 spectra have shown that CTA will be sensitive to this type of signatures with at least the E_{Pl} for the linear LIV coefficient [19, 20]. A Consortium paper, including these analyses, is currently (2019) under the Consortium review.

Figure 7: The simulated CTA observations of 1ES0229+200 with $E_{\text{cut}} = 40$ TeV without LIV effect (left) and with the LIV scenario $n = 2$ (right) [20]. The shaded band is the variation in the limits of the EBL model [30].

7 Absorption effects during extragalactic propagation

The star formation history of the universe will affect the radiation coming from distant AGNs, because part of the emission of these powerful sources is absorbed via pair production processes in photon-photon interactions,

$$\gamma_{\text{VHE}} + \gamma_{\text{EBL}} \rightarrow e^+ + e^- \quad (4)$$

where a VHE photon from an AGN annihilates with a low energy photon from the extragalactic background light (EBL) at an angle θ ($\mu = \cos \theta$) to produce an electron-positron pair. The main contributions to the EBL come from the integrated direct emission of stars (UV/optical) and secondary emission by dust scattering (IR), both integrated along the whole cosmological history. Its spectral intensity is maximum at wavelengths from the far-IR to UV. Therefore, the extragalactic medium will present a certain opacity to the gamma-rays, and the spectrum of a source measured at Earth, $\Phi_{\text{obs}}(E_\gamma, z_0)$, will be related to the intrinsic spectrum, $\Phi_{\text{int}}(E_\gamma, z)$, at the source redshift z by an attenuation function depending on the optical depth of the extragalactic medium, $\tau(E_\gamma, z)$

$$\Phi_{\text{obs}}(E_\gamma, z_0) = e^{-\tau(E_\gamma, z)} \Phi_{\text{int}}(E_\gamma, z). \quad (5)$$

The optical depth, in turn, can be obtained from the EBL photon number density $n(E_{\text{EBL}}, z)$ and the associated QED process cross-section $\sigma(E_\gamma, E_{\text{EBL}}, \mu)$ in an universe with expansion rate governed by dt/dz via [31, 32]

$$\tau(E_\gamma, z) = \frac{c}{2} \int_0^z dz' \frac{dt'}{dz'} \int_{-1}^1 d\mu (1 - \mu) \int_{E'_{\text{min}}}^{\infty} dE'_{\text{EBL}} \sigma(E'_\gamma, E'_{\text{EBL}}, \mu) n(E'_{\text{EBL}}, z), \quad (6)$$

Figure 8: *Left*: EBL energy density in comoving coordinates for an observer at $z = 0$ according to Finke et al model [33]. In addition to the total density (black curve), individual contributions are also shown coming from: stars (red - long dash), hot small dust grains (blue dotted), warm large grains (blue - dash-dot) and PAH (red dotted). Experimental points represent upper (yellow) and lower (green) limits. *Right*: Result of the combined fit of the intrinsic spectrum and relative contributions of dust grains using Mkn 501 measured SED, where the measured SED is superimposed to the convolution of the best-fit intrinsic spectrum with the attenuation factors of each EBL component, as well as the total attenuation [34].

where $E'_{\min} = \frac{2m_e c^2}{E'_\gamma(1-\mu)}$ is the threshold for pair-production and the relationship between emitted (primed) and observed at redshift z (unprimed) energies is $E' = (1+z)E$. The presence of the EBL, therefore, introduces a certain difficulty in distinguishing source intrinsic effects from those associated to the attenuation.

Nowadays, a few dozens of TeV extragalactic sources, most of them blazars, were detected and their spectra characterized, allowing upper limits on the EBL energy density to be imposed. The CTA is expected to bring both qualitative and quantitative changes to this scenario with its factor 10 improvement in sensitivity, fine angular and energy resolutions, allowing for more precise spectrum measurements and the discovery of a whole new population of TeV blazars at high redshifts. The availability of high quality measured SEDs of extragalactic TeV-emitters has opened up a new window for EBL attenuation studies, where one can perform combined fits of intrinsic source parameters as well as EBL variables provided this radiation field is suitably parameterized. Among the currently observed extragalactic sources with intense emissions at TeV is the blazar Markarian 501 (Mkn 501) at redshift $z = 0.034$. Its exceptional flare in 1997 was caught by HEGRA [35] which detected photons up to 20 TeV. As shown in [34], Mkn 501 is the gamma-ray source with the highest expected level of attenuation due to the dust component to the EBL. When suitable parameterizations for the intrinsic spectrum of Mkn 501, as well as for the EBL energy density (see the left-hand side of figure 8) are used, a combined fit of

Figure 9: *Left*: The posterior (in this case, also equal to the likelihood) as a function of the relative contribution of PAH (f_{PAH}) to the EBL. The black curve corresponds to 30min, the green one to 5h and the red to 50h of observation with CTA southern array. The vertical line corresponds to the true solution. *Right*: Superposition of the reconstructed SED for 50 h of observation with the predicted fluxes using the true (black and barely visible) and best-fit (red) values of f_{PAH} [36].

these parameters to the HEGRA measurements shows interesting constraints across the joint parameter space. The best-fit solution for the Mkn 501 SED can be seen in the right-hand side of figure 8, evincing the contribution of each one of the four EBL components considered (one stellar and three dust grains, i.e., emission from small hot grains, large warm grains and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, PAH, molecules).

In [36], absorption forecasts were performed using Monte Carlo simulations of CTA-south observational campaigns of extragalactic sources. The simulations were used to estimate the constraining power of the observatory to intrinsic parameters of the source spectrum as well as to dust parameters of the EBL according to the model of Finke et al [33]. The source parameters were sampled from a gamma-ray luminosity function tuned to Fermi-LAT data [37,38]. The left-hand side of figure 9 shows the behavior of the posterior probability distribution used as a function of a parameter of the EBL dust component, more precisely, the relative contribution (f_{PAH}) of PAH molecules, using three different duration of the observational campaigns (30 min, 5h and 50 h) of an extragalactic source at redshift $z = 0.0367$ with gamma-ray luminosity $\log(L_\gamma/\text{erg s}^{-1}) = 44.35$. The right-hand side of figure 9 shows the best-fit to the simulated SED for 50 hours of observation. When several sources measured at different redshifts are combined, there will be a large potential for breaking the degeneracy between intrinsic source spectral features and those introduced by the EBL attenuation.

Figure 10: MST telescope prototype in Berlin, Germany. The gray parts were projected and constructed in Brazil.

8 Instrumentation

We are also involved in the construction of the MST telescopes for CTA. The participation in the research in the instrumentation of the telescopes for CTA is a long project we have been working on during the last six years in collaboration with many foreign institutions in CTA as well as with Brazilian industries.

The MST are the tried and trusted telescopes of the CTA array. The MSTs are the ones responsible to push the sensitivity in the intermediate region to its minimum. The MST telescope has a Davies-Cotton [39] design with focus at 16 meters. Figure 10 shows the MST prototype in Berlin, Germany.

The development of the Camera Support Structure (CSS - gray parts in Figure 10) in partnership with the Brazilian companies is an important aspect of the participation of Brazil in CTA. It is an example of integration between industry and university, rarely seen in Brazil. As a prize for this effort, we manage to request the intellectual protection of one device developed for the CSS as a patent. Along the detailed design we realized the need for an adjustable device for the camera. The camera is attached to the CSS but the CSS must be able to adjust the camera position in three axes in order to place it with precision of the order of millimeters. We tried to buy an adjustable device to attached to the CSS however we found none which could move the 2.5 ton weight of the camera with such a precision. We therefore developed one based on the combination of three different metals in specific parts of the devices.

9 Final remarks

CTA will be the astroparticle physics experiment of the next decades. No other observatory will contribute to the understanding of many high energy astrophysical phenomena such as CTA will do. The authors of this paper are strongly involved in modeling, orienting and adjusting the potentiality of CTA, as well as in the construction of the telescopes. This paper had as target to illustrate the interest and work under development in this direction.

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